

SWINS

Sustainable Well-being
through INvestment
in Social Services

D9.2 Report on Framing, Narratives & Messaging

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Disclaimer

This Report has been prepared by Social Platform as part of Task 9.2 “Maximisation of the policy outcomes of the project”/ Work Package 9. This Task will focus on developing consistent and harmonised language around the project’s research and output, by developing and maintaining a structure and guidelines for the policy briefs (PB) contained in the WPs to make sure that findings and working papers of each work package follow the same structure, are jargon free and support the translation of the scientific findings in policy recommendations for evidence-based policy making at EU and global levels This deliverable contains original unpublished work except where clearly indicated otherwise. Acknowledgement of previously published material and of the work of others has been made through appropriate citation, quotation or both.

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1. Introduction

This report details the tools developed and activities implemented to ensure SWINS project partners' capacity to influence institutional frameworks, governance mechanisms, and policies at the EU level through the results produced across Work Packages. It also aims to lay the groundwork for a consistent and harmonised language across the project, as foreseen in the GA.

By following the rationale of the impact strategy and engaging with institutional stakeholders, policymakers, and other key actors, SWINS project will be able to contribute advancing the rights-based social investment paradigm, with tangible impact results.

In line with the impact strategy, the power mapping derived from D9.1 - Impact Strategy was put into context through stakeholders fiche and aligned to recent updates to policy priorities in EU level. However, the present deliverable also marks a first step in identifying common narratives, values and framings that can guide the development of coherent, audience-specific messages throughout the project.

A Guideline to policy briefs was developed within WP 9 activities, ensuring clear steps to their development, including explanations on their relevance; content; structure and its link to the work to be implemented within WP9 in collaboration with all partners. This guidance is accompanied by a shared template and recommendations that reflect the framing priorities of the project.

The Messaging Lab workshop is also part of such work, as detailed in the Annex section. It provided project partners with a clear overview of policy priorities and key stakeholders relevant for the SWINS project. This activity supported partners in making sense of the key targets for the project's outcomes and in identifying appropriate framings and channels in adapting messages, contents of policy briefs, interventions and other contributions accordingly. The policy context and policy briefs guidelines were then presented during the second Transnational project meeting, through a policy messaging workshop.

2. The Theoretical Framework narrative strategy for communication and impact

Given that SWINS project aims to generate high-quality research and meaningful policy engagement, communication and impact activities must be based on a shared conceptual structure to guide the articulation of coherent, context-sensitive messages. The Theoretical Framework (D2.1) is the key resource in this respect for all partners, and should represent the guiding document for all research and impact related activities.

Rather than imposing a single, fixed vision of social investment, SWINS starts from the assumption that the European policy landscape is shaped by multiple and sometimes competing narratives. These narratives reflect different priorities, values and expectations regarding the purpose of social services and policies, how they generate value and how they should be assessed. This multiplicity is not a weakness. On the contrary, it is a strategic asset for a project such as SWINS, which aims to engage with diverse audiences, including policymakers, service providers, civil society actors, and EU-level institutions.

To support this work, the Theoretical Framework identifies three major narrative layers currently at play in the European debate. These are not theoretical abstractions, but rather framing dimensions that influence how evidence is perceived and utilised in real-world decision-making processes. They serve as conceptual 'filters' that can help partners to tailor their messages while remaining anchored in the project's core values.

The first and currently hegemonic layer in the EU policy debate is built around **competitiveness**. This narrative has gained prominence in recent years, particularly in response to global geopolitical tensions, economic instability, and the perceived need to reinforce Europe's strategic autonomy. In this framing, social services and policies are understood primarily as investments in human capital, as enablers of labour market participation, and as contributors to productivity, innovation, and fiscal sustainability.

This is not a merely economic vision. It is a political discourse that responds to pressing policy concerns such as the future of work, the costs of demographic ageing, or the reform of public finances. The core message is: **investing in people today will reduce public spending tomorrow and support economic growth over time.**

This narrative is especially salient in institutional documents such as the Annual Single Market and Competitiveness Report (2024), sometimes referred to as the Competitiveness Compass. These documents redefine competitiveness as a broad concept that encompasses not only productivity but also technological sovereignty, energy security, and workforce readiness. Within this framework, the role of social services and policies is to prepare individuals to cope with change, to participate actively in economic life, and to contribute to the Union's strategic resilience.

From the point of view of SWINS, engaging with this narrative means highlighting the ways in which investment in social services and policies pays off, both economically and socially, when assessed

over an appropriate time horizon. This may include either showing how access to care and inclusion services improves workforce participation, particularly among women and vulnerable groups, or arguing that inclusive labour market policies enhance overall productivity and reduce long-term dependency.

This narrative is politically resonant and often required to open doors in high-level policy dialogues, especially when dealing with actors who prioritise budgetary constraints and economic performance indicators.

However, it is important to note that the competitiveness narrative, while dominant, does not exhaust the potential meanings and goals of social services and policies. Communicating solely within this frame risks reducing the richness of the project's vision and overlooking critical dimensions such as sustainability and social justice. Therefore, this layer should be seen as strategically useful, especially when linking SWINS to ongoing policy processes, but not sufficient on its own.

The second narrative layer framing the SWINS project is oriented towards **inclusive and sustainable well-being**. This perspective has gained traction in recent years, especially during and after the COVID-19 crisis, which prompted a rethinking of the European development model and led to the formulation of ambitious frameworks such as the European Green Deal and NextGenerationEU. In this narrative, investment in social services and policies is not merely a tool to enhance productivity or reduce public spending. Rather, it is seen as a transformative driver that enables a deep transition toward a more resilient, inclusive, and sustainable society. This includes rethinking how we measure progress, moving beyond GDP to integrate social cohesion, environmental balance, and collective capabilities into the policy agenda.

SWINS builds on this vision by proposing that investment in social services and policies should be framed as part of a broader societal shift, aiming to align economic development with the planetary boundaries and long-term well-being objectives. **The emphasis here is on interdependence: between people and their environments, between economic growth and social inclusion, and between present needs and future generations' rights.**

This narrative indeed resonates with international and EU-level strategies that seek to integrate the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development, the European Pillar of Social Rights, and the Just Transition mechanisms. In this frame, childcare, education, and social protection are viewed as public infrastructures essential to sustain inclusive transitions, as well as care and inclusion services are considered vital for building community resilience in the face of ecological, demographic and technological change. Therefore, social investment becomes a strategic lever to reconfigure society in a direction that is fairer and more sustainable.

From a communication and impact perspective, this narrative allows SWINS to connect with transformative policy agendas, progressive social movements, and forward-looking institutional actors. While it may not always be dominant in budgetary negotiations or economic planning, it is a powerful framing for mobilising stakeholders around long-term societal goals. Importantly, this layer also provides the conceptual space for reimagining social services as collective goods, not only as means to improve individual outcomes, but also as mechanisms to shape collective futures and democratic capacities.

The third and final narrative layer adopted by SWINS is rooted in the **rights-based approach**. This perspective considers investment in social services and policies not merely as a means to foster growth or manage transitions, but as a way to guarantee fundamental rights. These rights are enshrined in the European Pillar of Social Rights (EPSR) and in a broader set of international and constitutional commitments that define the European social model.

In this narrative, the primary justification for public investment in services such as healthcare, childcare, long-term care, education, and housing is the realisation of individual and collective rights. This implies a normative stance: even when such investments do not produce immediate economic

returns, or when their contribution to sustainability is indirect, they remain legitimate and necessary. From a messaging standpoint, this layer helps frame the ethical and legal foundation of SWINS. It also offers a powerful discursive resource to engage with actors concerned with social justice, anti-discrimination, and equal access to opportunities.

Key elements of this narrative include the idea of universalism and accessibility as cornerstones of social policy, together with empowerment and agency as central goals of service provision. The overall idea is that social rights should be fulfilled proactively, not passively or reactively, through adequate public investment.

Importantly, these layers are not mutually exclusive. They are different ways of expressing the same underlying commitment to inclusive and sustainable well-being, viewed through different lenses. They also correspond to different logics of justification: instrumental (competitiveness), systemic (sustainability) and normative (rights). Recognizing their complementarity, as well as their tensions, is essential for building impactful communication and advocacy strategies.

But what this means in practice? Following the SWINS attitude of always wondering about “So what?”, here is what these narratives represent for partners in practice:

- the competitiveness narrative allows SWINS to connect with institutional priorities and engage with economic actors and budgetary debates;
- the inclusive and sustainable wellbeing narrative positions SWINS within transformative and future-oriented agendas, appealing to progressive coalitions, environmental actors, and long-term policy planning;
- the rights-based narrative anchors the project in normative and legal frameworks, offering consistency, legitimacy, and a connection to social justice movements and constitutional principles.

These layers are useful internally to foster shared language and coherence among partners, and externally to tailor messages to diverse audiences. For this reason, we include here below a sort Glossary of keywords that must be used consistently throughout the project.

3. Keywords and common definitions

Social services and policies

The dual focus of SWINS: “services” refers to the infrastructures, interventions and delivery mechanisms that directly support individuals and communities; “policies” refers to the broader institutional frameworks and regulations that govern access, quality and funding of these services. This combined term avoids overly narrow or fragmented perspectives by embracing both in-kind and in-cash interventions.

Social investment

A policy approach that frames social spending as a long-term investment rather than a cost. It focuses on enhancing people’s capabilities, supporting human development over the life course, and fostering inclusive growth. In this way, appropriate social spending strategies are expected to create their own financial sustainability.

Rights-based social investment

Our distinctive vision of social investment rooted in the European Pillar of Social Rights (EPSR). It considers the fulfilment of social rights not merely as a means to achieve other goals but as an independent and normative objective. The primary return on investment, from this perspective, is the actual enjoyment of social rights by individuals.

European Pillar of Social Rights (EPSR)

The normative and institutional reference point for SWINS. The EPSR outlines 20 key principles to guide the development of fairer and more inclusive welfare systems in the EU. It underpins the project’s rights-based approach to social investment.

Inclusive and sustainable wellbeing

In SWINS, this concept frames the ultimate goal of social policies and services, guiding the transition beyond GDP-focused development models and toward resilient, rights-based and future-oriented welfare systems.

Transformative impact

In SWINS, transformative impact refers to the potential of social policies and services to foster the societal ability to shape new development pathways, support structural transitions and address the root causes of inequality and unsustainability.

Resilience

Not just the ability to withstand shocks, but to adapt and transform in the face of systemic challenges. In SWINS, resilience is linked to sustainable and inclusive well-being and is seen as a key outcome of investment in strong, equitable and sustainable social infrastructures.

Hegemonic / counter-hegemonic narratives

Competing discourses that shape public understanding and policy priorities. Drawing on Gramscian theory, SWINS identifies competitiveness, sustainability and rights as three narrative layers that are sometimes conflicting, sometimes complementary – all relevant for impact communication.

Multi-level governance

The system of policy-making across multiple institutional layers – from local to regional, national and EU levels. SWINS acknowledges that social investment strategies require coordination across governance levels, and engages with actors at each level through dialogue, co-creation and policy learning.

Social Investment as stabiliser

One of the systemic roles of social services and policies: to buffer societies against economic shocks, sustain internal demand, reduce inequalities and preserve democratic legitimacy. SWINS emphasises this function in contexts of crisis and transition.

Social Investment as an engine of transformation

By securing people wellbeing, strengthening social capital, preserving democratic legitimacy, social investment is a strategic asset to foster the deployment of transformative capacities at the societal level.

Enabling function

The role of social services and policies in creating the conditions for individuals and groups to participate meaningfully in society and the economy. This includes access to education, care, employment and civic engagement. The enabling function is central to capability expansion.

Policy learning

The process of mutual adaptation, experimentation and knowledge exchange between policy actors. SWINS supports policy learning through evidence-based recommendations, multi-actor engagement and iterative feedback loops.

Policy coherence

The alignment and integration of social, economic and environmental policies to ensure mutually reinforcing outcomes. SWINS advocates for coherence between social investment and broader EU goals such as green transition, inclusion and long-term resilience.

Investment logic

A framing strategy that positions social spending as an investment generating measurable returns, particularly when evaluated over an appropriate time span. This logic helps communicate the value of social policies in policy contexts dominated by fiscal constraints and competitiveness concerns.

4. Messaging house

Building on the narrative points mentioned above, the messaging house works as a quick guide to structure key messages when talking about investment on social services with EU policymakers, summarizing key aspects covered by SWINS project. It builds on the three interlinked narrative layers developed in the Theoretical Framework (competitiveness, sustainability, and rights) and translates them into adaptable communication formats. These narrative filters are not mutually exclusive: they provide different entry points for engaging diverse audiences, including policymakers, civil society, researchers, and the media.

Key message: Strategic investment in social services and policies has the potential to drive the EU's competitiveness, build long-term resilience, and ensure sustainable wellbeing.

Supporting messages

Investment in social services and policies must enable societies to adapt, innovate and build capabilities within planetary boundaries. It is a matter of economic and fiscal responsibility, rather than an expense.

Europe must move beyond short-term fiscal indicators to embrace a rights-based investment logic that captures the long-term social and economic outcomes of investment in people, aligning social goals with macroeconomic stability.

By investing in people, capabilities, and sustainable social infrastructure, the EU builds transformative resilience: the capacity to adapt, innovate, and thrive in a world of systemic shocks.

Foundation

Supporting argument 1: The returns on social investment increase over time, especially when policies are coordinated and sustained across different stages of life. Studies show that timely and well-calibrated investments in early education, labour market integration, and care infrastructures tend to generate more equitable, sustainable and resilient outcomes in the long run (see SWINS theoretical framework)

Supporting argument 2: 'productivity growth and social inclusion [must] go hand-in-hand.' The 2024 Draghi report on the Future of European Competitiveness, a roadmap for the European Commission for its competitiveness agenda, emphasizes that economic transformation can best lead to prosperity for all when grounded in a strong and inclusive social contract.

Supporting argument 3: We cannot rely on growth alone to ensure people's wellbeing. Indeed, there is only a minimal association between GDP growth and the increase of life satisfaction across countries (the Easterlin paradox, 2022). This highlights the importance of shifting towards investment

logics that prioritize inclusive and sustainable wellbeing, strengthening people’s resilience rather than narrowly focusing on output indicators.

Drawing on the three narrative layers outlined in the Theoretical Framework, the following table illustrates how these narrative filters can be used to frame the same project results in diverse, yet complementary, ways. These are just examples based on the domains covered by SWINS empirical work, but WP9 partners will be available to help all researchers in drafting their messages to maximize impact.

4.1. Examples of how to adapt messages to strategic narratives

Project result	Competitiveness framing	Sustainability framing	Rights-based framing
Improved access to childcare services	Boosts labour market participation and productivity, especially for women.	Supports inclusive resilience by enabling parents to balance care and work during socio-ecological transitions.	Realizes the EPSR principle on access to quality and affordable childcare as a fundamental social right.
Investment in upskilling for long-term unemployed	Increases human capital and reduces dependency on welfare.	Prepares workers for the green transition and enhances long-term adaptability.	Ensures equal access to education and decent employment opportunities.
Strengthened local health services	Reduces long-term healthcare costs and supports an efficient workforce.	Builds local resilience to climate-related health risks and demographic change.	Fulfils the right to health and care under EPSR and strengthens social inclusion.

Further examples on how messages can be translated into impactful narratives come from the Barcelona Policy Messaging Workshop, therefore from the partner themselves. Working in groups, SWINS partners were asked to formulate short pitches targeting different EU, national and regional stakeholders, using language tailored to the addressee while staying aligned with the project's overarching messages. These are a few examples extrapolated from this occasion.

4.2. Examples of framing from the Policy Messaging Workshop

Target stakeholder	Narrative filter	Example of tailored message
MEP – European People’s Party (EMPL Committee)	Competitiveness	<i>Europe’s competitiveness must rest on people, by investing in skills, innovation, and resilience that unveils social policy within a growth strategy.</i>
Commission expert – Anti-Poverty Strategy	Sustainability	<i>A sustainable competitiveness agenda must integrate social inclusion. Redefining competitiveness around inclusive prosperity links directly to social investment.</i>
Regional actor – Social protection system	Rights / Inclusion	<i>Regions can lead Europe’s shift toward sustainable competitiveness by investing in people and communities. Building resilience at local level means combining innovation and inclusion.</i>

5. Elevator pitch - SWINS in some 100 words

SWINS stands for Inclusive and Sustainable Well-Being through Investment in Social Services. The idea is simple but powerful: **social services and policies aren’t just a safety net**, they are the foundation for both people and the economy to thrive. This project translates complex evidence into clear, practical insights that show how investing in people, through care, education, and community services, can improve lives, strengthen communities and fuel sustainable growth.

What makes SWINS different is that it doesn’t frame social and economic goals as competing. In a time when Europe faces trade-offs between competitiveness, fiscal balance, and social rights, **SWINS builds bridges**. It shows that investing in social services and policies can do all of these things at once, unlocking a more inclusive, well-being-driven future for all.

6. Setting the scene – key stakeholders fiches

The SWINS policy impact strategy aims at ensuring the visibility and uptake of the project outcomes, with the overarching objective of contributing to systemic policy change. requires a comprehensive outreach approach engaging a wide range of institutional and societal stakeholders. This session focuses on outlining the main characteristics, interests, and influence pathways of the 'key players' identified in the SWINS power mapping, as presented in Deliverable D9.1 – Impact Strategy.

6.1. European Commission

The European Commission is the EU executive body responsible for proposing and monitoring the implementation of EU laws and budget. Its key attributions are proposing new legislation, implementing Council decisions and representing the EU in international agreements.

The Commission is also a focal point for agenda setting, as it is responsible for launching and implementing strategies, and proposing the EU budget. The laws, programmes and budget proposed by the Commission are nevertheless subject to scrutiny and approval by the Council and the European Parliament.

In addition to its core competences, the European Commission coordinates the European Semester process, through which Country-Specific Recommendations are issued and continuously monitored, drawing notably on analytical insights from the [Social Scoreboard](#) indicators.

The Commission is composed of 37 Directorate Generals (DGs), which are 'departments' with different focus areas, from Social Affairs to Fisheries. For SWINS project, the most strategic DGs are listed below:

DG Acronym	Topics, matters currently working on
DG EMPL	European Pillar of Social Rights Action Plan, Minimum Income Recommendation, Care Strategy, Skills Agenda
DG CLIMA	European Green Deal implementation, Just Transition Mechanism
DG ENV	Circular economy, environmental governance
DG RTD	Horizon Europe missions, European Research Area, social innovation, R&I for green and digital transitions
DG REGIO	Cohesion Policy 2021–2027, Territorial Just Transition Plans, urban development

DG NEAR	Enlargement and Neighbourhood Policy, Social and Economic Resilience in accession countries
DG GROW	Industrial Strategy, social economy, Public Procurement review
DG ENER	Just Transition in energy systems.
DG ECFIN	Economic governance reform, Stability and Growth Pact revision, European Semester, sustainable growth strategy, Recovery and Resilience Facility implementation
DG Eurostat	SDG indicators, quality of life framework, labour market and inequality data.
DG JRC	Resilience indicators, foresight report – intergenerational fairness index, social innovation, territorial analysis, SDG monitoring.

6.1.1. Interest to the project

The key priorities and work plan set by the Commission should be monitored to ensure that the approaches we adopt and deliverables we develop are tailored to current challenges and can be embedded to upcoming Commission plans and initiatives.

The Commission 2026 work programme lists many upcoming initiatives that are relevant to SWINS project, such as:

- Anti poverty Strategy (Q1 2026)
- Intergenerational Fairness Strategy (Q1 2026)
- Gender Equality Strategy (Q1 2026)
- Update of the Child Guarantee (Q2 2026)
- Update of rules on Public Procurement (Q2 2026)
- Global Health Resilience initiative (Q2 2026)
- Enhancing the strategy for the rights of persons with disabilities up to 2030 (Q2 2026)
- Skills portability initiative (Q3 2026)
- Quality Jobs Act (Q4 2026)

In addition, the European Pillar of Social Rights action plan will be published by Q4 2025.

Each initiative will rely on **key indicators; roadmaps for implementation and flagship initiatives**. SWINS can inform the development of social investment and wellbeing indicators, e.g. measuring *life-course returns* it contributes to the statistical underpinning of a “wellbeing economy” measurement and to the angle adopted in each of the relevant Commission works as targeted.

Examples

1. An overview on Lifelong learning models within Active Labour Market Policies can provide valuable insights to inform the Quality Jobs Act. In line with the timing for the project results, it is possible to plan dissemination on SWINS channels and to plan events and exchanges. The project visibility can also be increased by informing DG EMPL of relevant activities within the project that they can follow.

2. The forthcoming Anti poverty strategy is expected to include one target indicator centred on quality jobs. However, the multidimensional aspect of poverty and the need for a lifelong perspective to prevent deprivation will require going beyond active labour market policies, towards increased investment on comprehensive social protection systems. The SWINS framework can contribute to this agenda by providing an integrated model of social investment across different social policy domains, offering both strategic priorities and measurement tools to help achieve the EU’s long-term ambition of eradicating poverty by 2050, as articulated in the 2025 State of the Union address.

6.1.2. Relevant narratives

The DGs units will have varied needs and interests linked to their programmes, but one focal point to raise their interest is to build the case for **increased competitiveness** thanks to measurement systems that can facilitate the evaluation of investment effectiveness and a better framing of social services that responds to pressing needs on different areas (employment, care, inclusion, etc) with effects to resilience.

Therefore, key messages to address to the Commission are:

- **Investing in people is Europe's most sustainable growth strategy** and should not be framed as a fiscal burden. Investing in skills, innovation, and resilience under a life-course approach turns social policy into a growth strategy.
- **Integrating the life-course multiplier logic** can help assess the long-term fiscal and social returns of coordinated social investment, helping track Member States' capacity for sustainable and inclusive competitiveness.

6.1.3 Channels and modes of engagement

Commission expert groups and Advisory Boards – introduce SWINS frameworks to experts centred on social investment, resilience, social welfare indicators to support their work.

Contribution to [public consultations](#) - Shape the framing of emerging EU initiatives through common positions, introduce key concepts that must be integrated and make the position public.

Direct contact to inform on project outputs and upcoming events – reaching out to DGs' unit experts to match their current priorities and relevant files to the project results, with clear recommendations.

Targeted communication and events – towards increasing the visibility of a file under discussion across institutions and on key moments of the year, such as the European Semester and the Social Summit.

6.2. Council of the European Union

The Council of the European Union (The Council) is the main decision-making body within the EU. It brings together ministers of Member States to discuss on matters that concern their area of competence (e.g. social affairs; health; finances) and to ensure coordination across countries policies. Together with the European Parliament, the Council acts as a co-legislator, to amend and approve (or not) legislative proposals from the Commission. It is also responsible to adopt decisions (on crisis contexts), recommendations (non-binding) and to adopt the Country specific recommendations from the European Semester.

The Council presidency is set under a rotative trio presidency to ensure coordination and governance. The current presidency is under Denmark (July–December 2025), followed by Cyprus (January–June 2026); which will then be succeeded by a new trio formed by Ireland, Lithuania and Greece.

The Council is subdivided in 10 thematic groups aligned to the Ministers' area of competence. The most relevant group to SWINS project is the Employment, Social Policy, Health and Consumer Affairs Council (**EPSCO**), as it covers the core policy domains of social investment. In a nutshell, the EPSCO implements the European Pillar of Social Rights and implements soft coordination through the European Semester and the Social Protection Committee (SPC) to reach political commitment from Ministers of Social Affairs.

We also emphasize the importance of the Social Protection Committee (SPC), as an advisory policy Committee within EPSCO that monitors the social situation in the EU and the development of social protection policies. This Committee also follows the European Pillar of Social Rights.

6.2.1. Interest to the project

The EPSCO sets the tone of social reforms and framing of social investment through **coordination and benchmarking**. One of the main challenges addressed by the Council, specially EPSCO, is the coordination of social policies across countries, composed of different support models, levels of investment, services framing, competence levels, etc.

As in other institutions, the Council currently lacks a lifelong perspective and understanding on sustainable wellbeing approach to social investment, which leads to a siloed approach when dealing with social policies. More importantly, the increased role of the Council in addressing polycrises raises the importance to prioritise social policies under critical juncture for decision making and draws the opportunity to address such challenges through the lens of transformative resilience.

Overcoming the narrative of social spending towards transformative investment will therefore influence several aspects of the Council's work.

Examples

Evidence built from the Coleman boat (the macro-micro returns from investment on social services) can build the case for positioning social investment at the core of EU governance. This could support the Council to continually work on the European Pillar of Social Rights and its Action Plan towards increased social investment.

The Economic and Social Affairs Council (ECOFIN) coordinates economic policies and monitors budgetary policies, which can also shape the work of EPSCO.

If increased social investment is shown to contribute to strengthening economic resilience and sustainable growth, the EU's fiscal governance framework (under the competence of the ECOFIN Council) should also account for these long-term benefits and avoid pro-cyclical austerity measures that undermine them. This brings more substance to the work of EPSCO in coordinating and expanding social policies.

6.2.2. Relevant narratives

- SWINS provides the analytical case that **social investment contributes to more fiscal sustainability**. It supports the inclusion of social investment indicators in macroeconomic coordination and strengthens arguments for more structured social investment
- Investing in people and social infrastructure reduces long-term social liabilities and strengthens the EU's productive base.

6.2.3. Channels and modes of engagement

For SWINS project, the main channel of Influence and impact within the Council will be the outreach through informal meetings (EPSCO), as well as meetings with the presidency permanent representation; and messaging the ministry ahead of agenda setting to raise key points that concern social investment and that are covered in SWINS.

More importantly, the work of outreach to the Council relies strongly on early identification of opportunities that align with the work programme and the progress of the project. This should be monitored and brought to discussion by WP9.

6.3 European Parliament

The European Parliament is the only EU elected body, being a political forum for debate and decision-making while representing the interest of citizens in the EU. It acts as co-legislator along with the Council for new legislation and the approval of the EU annual budget, but also plays a key role in overseeing the work of the EU institutions and enforcing democracy.

The Parliament is divided in accordance with political parties, rather than per country. The MEPs meet on Plenary sessions for key discussions and votes but also organise their work through 22 different thematic Committees. Those Committees discuss the adoption of legislation, propose own-initiative reports, and draft opinions on the European Semester and other relevant matters in the scope of the Committee.

Within the SWINS project, the most relevant Parliament Committees are:

- EMPL – Employment and Social Affairs Committee
- ENVI - Environment, Public Health and Food Safety Committee
- CULT - Culture and Education Committee
- REGI - Regional Development Committee
- ECON - Economic and Monetary Affairs Committee

6.3.1. Interest in relation to the project

Social investment is cross-cutting, touching employment, education, health, gender equality, and green transition policies and therefore, strongly present on EU citizens daily lives. It is important to keep in mind that the Parliament will discuss on the grounds of the better framing for welfare, growth and socio-economic development across Europe, translating more technical frameworks into political commitments. Through the amendments on legislative text and positions, it will demand a coherent position from the Commission proposals, ensuring it is built in continuity with the social agenda and on the best interest of the EU.

Therefore, the project approach to social services and their transformative power gives the Parliament conceptual and empirical leverage to **build coherent political narratives and decisions** across Committees.

Examples

SWINS helps EMPL articulate social policy as productive and future-oriented. The life-course multiplier logic strengthens arguments for early childhood education, ALMPs, and care system, which supports an enabling framework and the planning of social investment strategies. Connecting sustainability to social inclusion brings relevant inputs to the work of ENVI in defending a fair and just transition. SWINS can support a governance logic linking health systems, environmental resilience, and social protection.

Demonstrating how investment in ECEC, care, lifelong learning and gender-sensitive employment policies drive inclusive growth reinforces the work of FEMM and CULT Committees.

6.3.2. Relevant narratives

Europe needs to move from fragmented national welfare systems to a coordinated, lifelong social investment strategy. The Parliament can champion a shift toward a *wellbeing-based, life-course perspective* that recognises how education, health, care, and employment policies reinforce one another over time. By embedding this logic into EU initiatives and budgetary instruments, MEPs can help ensure that social protection becomes a shared European commitment — not a patchwork of national efforts.

The Parliament should drive a political reframing of social spending as transformative investment. In an era of overlapping crises, coordinated social policies are not optional; they are Europe's best insurance against future shocks.

Embedding the transformative resilience approach into the EU's recovery and fiscal frameworks would allow social policy to shape, not follow, economic reform and efforts to ensure economic growth.

6.3.3. Channels and modes of engagement

Meeting with European party representatives – S&D, Renew Europe, The Left, Greens, EPP, etc to exchange on the results of the project and relevance in EU and national levels.

Organisation of events, promoted by a MEP, with targeted audience to raise current challenges and the ways forward.

Sharing project results to MEPs and their teams to enable informed decisions on legislative processes.

Developing targeted dissemination content to MEPs and stakeholders that also monitor the positions and activities of the Parliament Committees.

7. SWINS Policy Brief Guidelines

Policy briefs are short documents written by experts that present **policy recommendations** based on evidence. They are practical documents with concise information that can translate complex research data and results into actionable steps to policymakers, so they can take informed decisions to shape social policies. In other words, a policy brief targets a non-academic audience interested in the policy implication of the research.

Policy briefs can also be very useful to other types of stakeholders such as NGOs, research centres and associations that centre their work on advocacy, working as a tool to influence their work when approaching complex topics such as social investment.

A policy brief is **not a summary of an academic publication**. It is not meant to be a summary of the working paper with the policy flavour, but rather a reshape of its content highlighting the key policy implications and messages. It might go beyond the working paper or report, also because it is supposed to be released after the other publications and the policy context and landscape, that may have changed, must be considered.

We describe here key steps to prepare and compose quality briefs that can support promoting the results of SWINS project to interested audiences.

7.1. Context behind the policy brief

When preparing the policy brief, you should make sure to:

1. **Understand the current policy priorities** in the relevant domain (e.g, at the EU level, at the national level in a particular country, etc.) through recent developments – elections, recent official statements, new action plans and strategies, etc. This can be consulted within this guide and further discussed updated through developments uncovered by the activities within WP9.
2. **Identify the challenges** to be addressed through the policy brief, and how your policy brief will help contribute to a solution. Doing this preliminary research will back up the content delivered through the policy brief.
3. **Identify your primary target audience(s)**: EU policymakers? National institutions? Academic scholars? Civil society? Knowing who your target audience can help you target the language and framing of the policy brief to the right reader. Key targets are listed on the Power Mapping of D9.1 – Impact Strategy, for your reference, and briefly described on the stakeholders fiches in this document, but can also be further assessed.

Key point: to ensure a good contextualization, set a meeting with WP9 leaders to obtain updates, insights and identify focal points to shaping the policy brief.

7.2. Content

2. **Assess the language** to be used and what jargon and key words may need to be adopted to better frame it to targeted audiences. Besides avoiding very technical language, it is important to review the text to avoid some terms that can lead to ambiguity or unfocused reading. E.g.: 'to simplify', which in some EU contexts is used as synonym to de-regulate; 'to institutionalize', which is avoided when talking about social inclusion, as it can refer to the condition of segregation faced by persons with disabilities on medical services; etc.
3. **Write engaging key policy highlights in bullet points** rather than an abstract: presenting results at the outset is crucial for an audience who is short on time. As opposed to academic writing, bullet points are more typical than an abstract as they can be more quickly read and digested.
3. **Include a background section:** try to answer for the reader what key questions they might have from the start so they see why they should keep reading: what is the problem? Why is this relevant? Why do we need to discuss this? What is the current policy context?
4. **Make it policy relevant:** explain how your proposal fits with existing policies and regulations (e.g., challenges or obstacles to implementation), but also existing gaps that could be filled with our initiatives. Present supporting evidence and provide clear, actionable policy recommendations.

Key point: after setting the context and explaining the relevance of the topics addressed, make recommendations that are policy relevant. To this aim, focus not only on 'what', but also 'how'. This is a key point to ensure that a policy brief is tailored to current challenges and reflects on possible ways forward. E.g:

'Member States must prioritise both the social and green dimensions of the public procurement processes (what), by enforcing the implementation of the 2014 EU Public Procurement Directive (how), and not consistently awarding the lowest bid.

7.3. Format

1. **Keep it concise:** (max 2.000 words). See the template here [LINK].
2. **Use plain language:** avoid jargon and technical language, as well as abbreviations and acronyms, that may confuse your audience. Use clear, short, and simple language to ensure your message is accessible to a wide range of readers.
3. **Include visuals:** use narratives and visualisations to better adapt the content to your audience; Try to include one chart or table that really illustrates your message(s). Graphics and descriptive boards that can summarize core ideas and guide the audience to follow through your arguments and solutions proposed.

7.4. Structure

The mandatory outline to SWINS Policy Briefs is:

- **Key messages:** briefly summarise the purpose and usefulness of the work done (max 4-5 messages, approximately 25 words each).
- **Background and context:** the section of the policy brief that provides an overview of the issue addressed and the motivation for studying that problem (around 600-700 words).
- **Evidence:** section in which the results of the working paper or report are presented in an attractive manner and in language that can be understood by the chosen stakeholders (around 500-600 words).
- **Policy recommendations and conclusions:** highlight policy recommendations that may result from the work with a concluding remark (max 5 recommendations, around 120 words each).
- **References and other info on authors affiliation** (around 100 words).

One practical example - [SWINS PolicyBrief TF web.pdf](#)

For necessary adaptations to length, format and language, please consult WP9 and WP10 leaders for discussion.

7.5. Policy Brief review process

After drafting the policy brief, it is necessary to ensure its alignment to policy priorities, messaging and target audiences by checking with SWINS partners involved on impact outreach (WP9) and dissemination (WP10). An appropriate timing for feedback must be allocated to receive inputs from such partners after version 1 is in place, and a final read of the final version before submission.

Timeline:

- Draft 1 shared for feedback – 4 weeks before submission deadline
- Feedback by WP9 and WP10 – 2 weeks before the submission deadline
- Policy Brief Final version – 1 week before submission deadline
- Final reading and approval – 4 days before submission deadline

Go further

Consider dissemination and advocacy: under consultation to WP10 and WP9 leaders, think about how your policy briefs can be distributed, providing suggestions that can complement the promotion of the material. For example using social media, events, press releases, or academic presentations to reach your target audience, but also reach members of consultative committees, experts currently working on related topics in national and EU levels, development of public consultations, webinars to CSOs, etc.

For example: policymakers rarely read academic papers, but follow blogs, use X/Twitter and listen to podcasts. Remember that they seek robust and easily digestible scientific evidence.

The policy briefs can also be adopted to raise the interest of audiences of experts, interested people having grasped the main rationale and outcomes before focusing on more complex deliverables.

The Policy Messaging Workshop (held in Barcelona in occasion of the Consortium Meeting, October 2025) powerpoint is included in Annex.

Annexes

Policy Messaging workshop - Main outcomes

National/ Regional/ Local impact

Facilitator: Gabriela Teixeira, Communications Assistant at Social Platform

The aim of this interactive session was to stimulate partners' contribution to the outreach strategy, and to obtain key insights on possible actions and key messages to increase SWINS visibility and multi-level impact. Partners were presented to a table of priority (low, medium, high) and were asked to consider the level of priority attributed to social policies (Early childhood care, long term care, access to education, access to employment, others) on a given country of their interest.

Group 1

Names: András Gábos, Réka Branyiczki, Nicole Kormann, Anne Skevik Grødem, Monica Mi Ah Schøyen, Rune Halvorsen, Floore Bursens, Jelena Zarkovic, Nemanja Vuksanovic

For this exercise, the primary country given as example was Sweden. In Sweden, stakeholders attribute varying levels of priority to key social issues. Early childhood care is considered a medium priority, gaining visibility in policy discussions but still unevenly implemented. Housing remains a low priority, receiving limited political and public attention despite its social relevance. Access to training and education and employment quality are seen as high priorities, though focus on the latter appears to be declining. Long-term and informal care occupy a medium-to-high priority, reflecting growing concern over the aging population and care infrastructure.

To promote the project effectively, opportunities lie in engaging EU-level and umbrella associations that influence both national and local stakeholders, given Sweden's reliance on EU funding in social programs. Strengthening partnerships with municipalities and regional actors can enhance local implementation and visibility. For low-priority areas like housing, awareness campaigns and collaboration with citizen and tenants' associations could help bridge the gap between public needs and policy attention, fostering broader engagement and political will. During the discussion, policies in Spain and Italy were also reviewed for comparison and insight.

Group 2

Names: Charlotte Fernandez, Margarita León, Zyab Luis Ibañez Garzaran, Federico Ciani, Salmasi Luca, Turati Gilberto, Charles O'Sullivan, Barbara Palla, Gerlinde Verbist, Toon Van Havere

For this exercise, the primary country given as example was Hungary. In Hungary, social priorities vary across key policy areas. Early childhood care, long-term care, and informal care remain low priorities, with limited public debate and weak policy frameworks. Housing and access to quality employment are medium priorities, featured in some governmental programs but inconsistently implemented. Access to training and education is viewed as a high priority, driven by concerns over low productivity and competitiveness. However, the centralized education system and the lowered compulsory schooling age (now 16) create challenges for long-term skill development and inclusion.

Opportunities to promote projects in medium- and high-priority areas include engaging national and regional stakeholders through initiatives that clearly demonstrate economic and social benefits, such as enhanced workforce skills and improved job quality. Collaboration with ministries, employers, and local governments could strengthen policy alignment and implementation. For low-priority areas, awareness campaigns and cross-sector dialogues can raise visibility and encourage action. It is also important to examine the WP2 and WP8 legal package to identify which aspects are centralized and how these could be addressed to enable more flexible and effective interventions. Even within a national system, certain issues may remain low-level, and understanding this structure is key to designing strategies that build momentum for reform and promote progress across all levels.

Accessible and Impactful writing

Facilitator: Ana Hannotte, Policy and Projects Officer at Social Platform

The aim of this session was to let partners discuss on forms to shape messaging based on complex information, to ensure impactful content in line with the guidance provided during the workshop presentation. Each group received one paragraph deriving from D 2.1 – Theoretical Framework and worked on highlighting key elements to develop an elevator pitch to a targeted audience of policymakers:

- One MEP from the European People’s Party – Liberal, has majority in the parliament and is one of the leads on EMPL Committee;
- One Commission expert working directly with the rapporteur of the upcoming Anti-Poverty Strategy;
- One representative of the regional system of social protection in your country;
- One Adviser to the European Semester process

Partners reflected on the need to shape the same message to similar audiences, especially in more informal contexts. It was important to pay attention to the length of the phrase as a typical elevator pitch, being concise through the use of key words that can raise the interest of the target audience. The aim is not to explain the entire framework in one phrase, but to raise the interest of the interlocutor and as such, go one step further in the promotion of the project and its results.

Group 1

Names: Charlotte Fernandez, Margarita León, Zyab Luis Ibañez Garzaran, Federico Ciani, Salmasi Luca, Turati Gilberto, Charles O’Sullivan, Barbara Palla, Gerlinde Verbist, Toon Van Havere

Key messages:

MEP from the European People’s Party

Europe’s competitiveness must rest on people, by investing in skills, innovation, and resilience that unveils social policy within a growth strategy. A life-course approach modernises Europe’s welfare model and strengthens participation, productivity, and social cohesion.

Commission Expert (Anti-Poverty Strategy)

“A sustainable competitiveness agenda must integrate social inclusion. Redefining competitiveness around inclusive prosperity links directly to social investment — addressing poverty at its roots by enhancing human capabilities and participation across the life course.”

Representative of Regional Social Protection System

“Regions can lead Europe’s shift toward sustainable competitiveness by investing in people and communities.

Building resilience at regional level means creating ecosystems that combine innovation, inclusion, and sustainability — where social policies are seen as productive investments in long-term competitiveness.”

Group 2

Names: András Gábos, Réka Branyiczki, Nicole Kormann, Anne Skevik Grødem, Monica Mi Ah Schøyen, Rune Halvorsen, Floore Bursens, Jelena Zarkovic, Nemanja Vuksanovic

Key messages:

EPP MEP (EMPL Committee)

Europe’s welfare model should work like an investment chain — early, enabling, and protective policies reinforcing one another over time.

If we put into historical perspective, social investment has been at the core of liberal policies in Europe. By sequencing interventions across the life course — from early childhood to active ageing — we can boost participation, productivity, and inclusion. This is how social policy becomes a growth strategy.”

Commission Expert (Anti-Poverty Strategy)

A life-course multiplier approach makes poverty prevention systemic and with direct effects to early childhood, family households and tackling poverty.

When early, enabling, and protective services are strategically combined, they generate cumulative returns — preventing deprivation from re-emerging later in life and strengthening long-term social inclusion.”

Adviser to the European Semester Process

“Integrating the life-course multiplier logic into the Semester can reveal the long-term fiscal and social returns of coordinated social investment.

Recognising how early and enabling policies compound over time would allow the Semester to better assess Member States’ structural resilience and sustainability.”

SWINS

Sustainable Well-being
through INvestment
in Social Services

Policy messaging Workshop

Ana Luiza Hannotte

Policy and Projects Officer – Social Platform

Funded by European Union's Horizon Europe
Programme under Grant Agreement No. 101177566

Introduction and Agenda

1

Obtain a clear understanding of EU Policy priorities and trends shaping social services

- Overarching Policy priorities
- Danish presidency; presidency program (upcoming Cyprus and Ireland)
- SOTEU
- Upcoming Strategies and acts
- Other sources

2

Be confident on developing accessible and impactful messages to targeted audience

- SWINS Power mapping
- Key stakeholders
- Policy Briefs – strategy
- Key guidelines - Shaping messages to ensure stakeholders outreach

3

Put into practice, share ideas and clarify key elements to build SWINS messages

World café session (45')

- National/ regional/ local impact
- Accessible and impactful writing
- Academic impact

Wrap-up – main outcomes

SOTEU 2025

Strong focus on Defense and Competitiveness - support to industry and agriculture

Highlights:

- «Help eradicate poverty by 2050 – Anti Poverty Strategy»
- Quality Jobs **Act**
- Housing as a social issue - Affordable Housing plan
- Social Climate Fund
- Competitiveness fund

Missing: a clearer commitment to social investment, A focus on the upcoming European Pillar of Social Rights

PORTO SOCIAL FORUM 2025

Porto Social Forum

A new target to quality jobs within the Anti Poverty Strategy, announced by Mînzatu

EU Strategic Foresight report 2025

Intergenerational Fairness

- JRC – upcoming Intergenerational fairness index (March 2026)

European Commission proposal to the next MFF (July 2025)

National Regional Partnership Plans

Be Confident on the key steps and resources to develop accessible and impactful writing

<p>Meet their needs</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • EU policy-makers/institutions • Council of the EU (ECOFIN Council, preparatory committees EPC, relevant Council working parties) • Council Presidencies (Poland, Denmark, Cyprus, Ireland, Lithuania, Greece) • European Investment Bank • National / local policymakers: • political representatives and civil servants in national and local governments. • Direct contacts at national/local level in selected European countries in which SWINS partners are located 	<p>Key player</p> <p>EU policy-makers/institutions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • European Commission DGs (EMPL, DG BUDG, SG REFORM, DG REGIO, DG RTD, SG, GROW, ECFIN, ESTAT) • Relevant Executive Vice-Presidents/Commissioners and their cabinets (Stéphane Séjourné - Prosperity and Industrial strategy, Raffaele Fitto - Cohesion and Reforms, Roxana Minzatu - Social Rights and skills, quality jobs and preparedness, Maroš Šefčovič- Trade and Economic Security Interinstitutional Relations and Transparency, Valdis Dombrovskis Economy and Productivity Implementation and Simplification) • Council of the EU (EPSCO Council preparatory committees SPC & EMCO) • Council Presidencies (Poland, Denmark, Cyprus, Ireland, Lithuania, Greece) • European Parliament (key committees: EMPL, ECON and committee chairs; Intergroup Intergroup on the Social Economy and Services of General Interest) • EC Joint Research Centre • European Parliamentary Research Service • Council of Europe <p>National / local policymakers:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • political representatives and civil servants in national and local governments. • Access through SPC-EMCO meeting
<p>Least important</p> <p>Qualified stakeholders</p> <p>Foundations: FEPS, Green European Foundation, Heinrich Böll, European Liberal Forum, Rosa Luxemburg foundation</p>	<p>Show consideration</p> <p>EU policy-makers/institutions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Executive Agencies and Committees (EESC, Committee of the Regions, • EIGE, Eurofound, <p>Qualified stakeholders</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Social Partners (EPSU, ETUI, ITUC, Business Europe, SGI Europe, SME United) • Think tanks (EPC, ZOE institute, CEPS, Bruegel, CMCC) • European advocacy networks and platforms (Social Platform members, SDG Watch Europe, Social Services Europe) • Local and Regional Governments' associations (Eurocities) <p>Scientific community:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • young, mid-career and senior researchers, scientific associations and top journals in social sciences engaged with research on sustainable development. • ERSA (European Regional Science Association) • ESA (European Sociological Association) • EADI (European Association of Development Research and Training Institutions)

Policy Makers and Institutions

EUROPEAN COMMISSION

DG EMPL, DG GROW, DG RTD, DG NEAR,
DG REGIO, DG ECFIN, DG JUST

Unit experts, rapporteurs, etc.

JRC – Joint Research Centre

Eurostat

POWER MAPPING LEVEL – KEY PLAYERS

What do they need?

Key insights on policy design applicable to upcoming programme :

- Which approaches to adopt? Are they innovative and cost-efficient?
- What are the outcomes of adopting a new approach, target, monitoring system, etc as proposed by the project
- How to (and to which actors) allocate resources?

Policy Makers and Institutions

COUNCIL OF THE EUROPEAN

EPSCO - Employment, Social Policy, Health and Consumer Affairs Council

Council presidencies (trilogues)

- Denmark
- Cyprus
- Ireland

POWER MAPPING LEVEL – KEY PLAYERS

What do they need?

Ensure social and civil dialogue to bring in social partners' perspective on key social policies

Expertise to orient the activities within the Council presidencies, aligned to key priorities of the social agenda: EPSR action plan; Anti poverty Strategy; Affordable Housing plan; upcoming topics.

Policy Makers and Institutions

EUROPEAN PARLIAMENT

Committees: Employment and Social Affairs; Health; Regional Development

Members of the European Parliament

POWER MAPPING LEVEL – KEY PLAYERS

What do they need?

Up to date evidence to sustain positions when proposing new legislation

Expert inputs throughout legislative process, for voting, endorsing flagship initiatives, joining campaigns, etc.

Aims and Strategy of Policy Briefs

1. Translate complex research data and results into actionable steps to policymakers
2. Amplify the project impact by boosting the adoption of deliverables by experts and key stakeholders

Policy Briefs - Guidelines

Understand the current policy priorities

Identify the challenges

Identify the primary target audience

Policy brief Guidelines
(available on wp9 folder)

Meeting with the WP9 lead and team to get
updates and new insights

Policy Briefs - Guidelines

Content

Assess the language

Write engaging key policy highlights in bullet points

Include a background section

Make it policy relevant: do not focus only on the 'what', but on the 'how'

Resources

Policy brief Guidelines
(available on wp9 folder)

Meeting with the WP9 lead and team to get updates and new insights

Policy Briefs - Guidelines

Content - examples

Social Platform's Position on the Anti-Poverty Strategy

The Anti-Poverty Strategy must: Ensure that EU resources under the next MFF are used effectively and have specific earmarkings

What

Earmarking must be used to support local initiatives aimed at reducing poverty and social exclusion (e.g. European Social Fund Plus, European Regional Development Fund, Just Transition Fund, programmes supporting education, research, inclusion, integration, civil engagement objectives).

How

Policy Briefs - Guidelines

Content - examples

Social Platform's recommendation – Rebalancing the European Green Deal

Member States must prioritise both the social and green dimensions of the public procurement processes, **by** enforcing the implementation of the 2014 EU Public Procurement Directive, and not consistently awarding the lowest bid.

What

How

Policy Briefs - Guidelines

Format

Keep it concise: (max 2.000 words)

Use plain language

Include visuals

Resources

Policy brief **Template**
(Check WP10 folder)

WP9 and WP 10 content and format checkup

Policy Briefs - Guidelines

General Structure

- **Key messages:** briefly summarise the purpose and usefulness of the work done (max 4-5 messages, approximately 25 words each).
- **Background and context:** the section of the policy brief that provides an overview of the issue addressed and the motivation for studying that problem (around 600-700 words).
- **Evidence:** section in which the results of the working paper or report are presented in an attractive manner and in language that can be understood by the chosen stakeholders (around 500-600 words).
- **Policy recommendations and conclusions:** highlight policy recommendations that may result from the work with a concluding remark (max 5 recommendations, around 120 words each).
- **References and other info on authors affiliation** (around 100 words).

Q&A

1 - National/ regional/ local impact

SWINS partners will share their views on national/regional/local context and identify potential stakeholders and opportunities to share project results and ensure impact outreach.

2 - Accessible and Impactful writing

Discuss on forms to shape messaging to ensure impactful content in line with the guidance provided on the presentation

3

OUTCOMES – 10 MINUTES

3 - Academic impact

Shape in few phrases the main outcome we seek to produce with the upcoming deliverables

Groups

Group 1	Group 2
András Gábos	Charlotte Fernandez
Réka Branyiczki	Margarita León
Nicole Kormann	Zyab Luis Ibañez Garzaran
Anne Skevik Grødem	Federico Ciani
Monica Mi Ah Schøyen	Salmasi Luca
Rune Halvorsen	Turati Gilberto
Floore Bursens	Charles O'Sullivan
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Nemanja Vuksanovic	Gerlinde Verbist
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Partners

UAB Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona

PIN
FOUNDATION
PRATO
CAMPUS
UNIVERSITY
OF FLORENCE

SWINS
Sustainable Well-Being
through Investments
in Social Services
sustainablewellbeing.eu

